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HIGH-PRECISION SOLUTION OF ELASTICITY PROBLEM FOR A LAYER ON CYLINDRICAL CUT-IN SUPPORTS WITH AN ELASTIC CYLINDRICAL INCLUSION

Abstract.

A three-dimensional elasticity problem is solved for a layer with a longitudinal cylindrical elastic inclusion, rigidly fixed on embedded cylindrical supports. The model is represented as an infinite layer with three longitudinal cylindrical cavities. One of the cavities contains a solid cylindrical inclusion, while zero displacements are specified on the other two cavities. Stresses are specified on the flat surfaces of the layer. The problem is solved using the generalized Fourier method in different coordinate systems. A numerical analysis of the stress state of the layer and the inclusion is performed, and the most dangerous areas are identified.

Keywords: layer with cylindrical cavities; generalized Fourier method, layer with cylindrical inclusions.

Introduction. When designing parts and mechanisms in aviation and mechanical engineering, one has to deal with various computational models of the stress-strain state. Most of these models are complex, and the choice of the calculation method becomes an important factor in obtaining the most accurate result.

Flush cylindrical supports are used for connections between different bodies. Such a node is complex in terms of choosing a method. Usually, such models are calculated using the finite element method [1]. However, numerical methods, which include the finite element method, are approximate and do not give confidence in the final result.

Another approach is the exact methods [2, 3], which solve the problem for a layer with a cylindrical cavity or inclusion. These methods are based on the expansion of the solution in a Fourier series. However, the proposed method does not allow solving problems with the number of boundary surfaces greater than three.

The most efficient analytical and numerical method for the presented model is the generalized Fourier method [4]. This method combines the basic solutions of the Lamé equation in different coordinate systems. This allows us to take into account any number of different canonical surfaces and to obtain a result with high accuracy.

The problems for a cylinder with cylindrical cavities or inclusions [5-7], a half-space [8], or a layer [9]

$F\vec{U}(x, z)_{y=h} = \vec{F}_h^0(x, z)$, $F\vec{U}(x, z)_{y=-\tilde{h}} = \vec{F}_{\tilde{h}}^0(x, z)$, on the boundaries of the layer:

$$\vec{U}(\varphi_\rho, z)_{\rho=R_p} = \vec{F}_p^0(\varphi_\rho, z),$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{F}_h^0(x, z) &= \tau_{yx}^{(h)} \vec{e}_x + \sigma_y^{(h)} \vec{e}_y + \tau_{yz}^{(h)} \vec{e}_z, \\ \vec{F}_{\tilde{h}}^0(x, z) &= \tau_{yx}^{(\tilde{h})} \vec{e}_x + \sigma_y^{(\tilde{h})} \vec{e}_y + \tau_{yz}^{(\tilde{h})} \vec{e}_z, \\ \vec{F}_p^0(\varphi_\rho, z) &= U_\rho^{(p)} \vec{e}_\rho + U_\varphi^{(p)} \vec{e}_\varphi + U_z^{(p)} \vec{e}_z, \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

with one cylindrical cavity, a layer with one cylindrical inclusion [10] have been solved using the generalized Fourier method. A number of problems for a layer with several cavities [11] or inclusions [12] have also been solved. However, the solution methods in the proposed works do not allow obtaining a result for a layer with two cylindrical cavities (with given displacements on them) and a cylindrical inclusion. To solve this problem, it is necessary to take into account other boundary conditions in combination with the conjugation conditions.

Problem statement. A set of N circular cylindrical inhomogeneities of radius R_p , where p is the inhomogeneity number, $p=1, 2, 3$, is located in an elastic homogeneous layer.

Circular cylindrical inhomogeneities will be considered in local cylindrical coordinate systems (ρ_p, φ_p, z) , a layer in the Cartesian coordinate system (x, y, z) , which is equally oriented and combined with the inclusion coordinate system ($p=1$). The upper boundary of the layer is located at a distance $y=h$, the lower boundary at a distance $y=-\tilde{h}$. It is necessary to find the solution of the Lamé equation under the conditions that the stresses are given

known functions.

All given vectors and functions will be considered rapidly decaying to zero at distances far from the origin in the z-coordinate for cavity surfaces and in the x- and z-coordinates for layer boundaries.

Research Methodology. Let's choose the basic solutions of the Lamé equation in the form [4]:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{u}_k^\pm(x, y, z; \lambda, \mu) &= N_k^{(d)} e^{i(\lambda z + \mu x) \pm \gamma y}, \\ \vec{R}_{k,m}(\rho, \varphi, z; \lambda) &= N_k^{(p)} I_m(\lambda \rho) e^{i(\lambda z + m \varphi)}, \\ \vec{S}_{k,m}(\rho, \varphi, z; \lambda) &= N_k^{(p)} \left[(\text{sign } \lambda)^m K_m(|\lambda| \rho) \cdot e^{i(\lambda z + m \varphi)} \right] k = 1, 2, 3; \\ N_1^{(d)} &= \frac{1}{\lambda} \nabla; N_2^{(d)} = \frac{4}{\lambda} (\nu - 1) \vec{e}_2^{(1)} + \frac{1}{\lambda} \nabla(y \cdot); N_3^{(d)} = \frac{i}{\lambda} \text{rot}(\vec{e}_3^{(1)} \cdot); N_1^{(p)} = \frac{1}{\lambda} \nabla; \\ N_2^{(p)} &= \frac{1}{\lambda} \left[\nabla \left(\rho \frac{\partial}{\partial \rho} \right) + 4(\nu - 1) \left(\nabla - \vec{e}_3^{(2)} \frac{\partial}{\partial z} \right) \right]; N_3^{(p)} = \frac{i}{\lambda} \text{rot}(\vec{e}_3^{(2)} \cdot); \\ \gamma &= \sqrt{\lambda^2 + \mu^2}, \quad -\infty < \lambda, \mu < \infty, \end{aligned} \tag{2}$$

where ν – Poisson coefficient; $I_m(x)$, $K_m(x)$ – modified Bessel functions; $\vec{R}_{k,m}$, $\vec{S}_{k,m}$, $k=1, 2, 3$ – internal and external solutions of the Lamé equation for a cylinder accordingly; $\vec{u}_k^{(-)}$, $\vec{u}_k^{(+)}$ – solutions of Lamé's equation for a layer.

The solution to the problem is presented as a combination of [11, 12]:

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{U}_0 &= \sum_{k=1}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} (H_k(\lambda, \mu) \cdot \vec{u}_k^{(+)}(x, y, z; \lambda, \mu) + \tilde{H}_k(\lambda, \mu) \cdot \vec{u}_k^{(-)}(x, y, z; \lambda, \mu)) d\mu d\lambda + \\ &+ \sum_{p=1}^3 \sum_{k=1}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} B_{k,m}^{(p)}(\lambda) \cdot \vec{S}_{k,m}(\rho_p, \varphi_p, z; \lambda) d\lambda, \\ \vec{U}_1 &= \sum_{k=1}^3 \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-\infty}^{\infty} A_{k,m}(\lambda) \cdot \vec{R}_{k,m}(\rho_1, \varphi_1, z; \lambda) d\lambda, \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where $\vec{S}_{k,m}(\rho_p, \varphi_p, z; \lambda)$, $\vec{u}_k^{(+)}(x, y, z; \lambda, \mu)$, $\vec{u}_k^{(-)}(x, y, z; \lambda, \mu)$ and $\vec{R}_{k,m}(\rho_1, \varphi_1, z; \lambda)$ are the basic solutions are given by formulas (2), and six unknown functions $H_k(\lambda, \mu)$, $\tilde{H}_k(\lambda, \mu)$, $B_{k,m}^{(p)}(\lambda)$ and $A_{k,m}(\lambda)$ must be found from the boundary conditions.

To find six unknowns, we write six equations: satisfaction of the boundary conditions at the upper and lower boundaries of the layer, on the surfaces of the cylinders $p = 2$ and $p = 3$ and two additional equations in the form of conjugation conditions between the layer and the inclusion ($p = 1$):

$$\begin{aligned} \vec{U}_0(\varphi, z)_{\rho=R_1} &= \vec{U}_1(\varphi, z)_{\rho=R_1}, \\ F\vec{U}_0(\varphi, z)_{\rho=R_1} &= F\vec{U}_1(\varphi, z)_{\rho=R_1}. \end{aligned}$$

To satisfy the boundary conditions, we represent the function (1) through the double Fourier integral for the layer and the Fourier integral with the Fourier series expansion for the cylinders.

To transform basic solutions between coordinate systems, we will use the formulas [12].

After solving the system of equations, all the unknowns of the equation (3) are found.

For the obtained systems, using the obtained determinants, their unique solvability is proved. Moreover, these systems can be solved by the

truncation method, and the convergence of approximate solutions to the exact one takes place.

Results and Discussion. In an elastic isotropic layer, two cylindrical cavities and a cylindrical inclusion are located parallel to its surface. The layer is made of plastic with a Poisson's ratio of $\nu_0 = 0.38$ and an elastic modulus of $E_0 = 1.7 \cdot 10^3$ MPa. The inclusion is made of steel with a Poisson's ratio of $\nu_1 = 0.25$ and an elastic modulus of $E_1 = 2 \cdot 10^5$ MPa.

Distance from the inclusion center to the upper and lower boundaries of the $h = \tilde{h} = 12$ mm layer. Radii of the inhomogeneities $R_1 = R_2 = R_3 = 5$ mm. Distance from the inclusion to the cavities $p = 2$ and $p = 3$: $L_{12} = L_{13} = 30$ mm, $\alpha_{12} = 0$, $\alpha_{13} = \pi$.

On the top surface of the layer, the stresses are given as

$$\sigma_y^{(h)}(x, z) = -10^8 \cdot (z^2 + 10^2)^{-2} \cdot (x^2 + 10^2)^{-2},$$

$\tau_{yx}^{(h)} = \tau_{yz}^{(h)} = 0$. On the bottom boundary of the layer, the stresses are given as

$\sigma_y^{(\tilde{h})}(x, z) = \tau_{yx}^{(\tilde{h})} = \tau_{yz}^{(\tilde{h})} = 0$. On the cavity surfaces, the displacements are given as $U_\rho^{(p)} = U_\varphi^{(p)} = U_z^{(p)} = 0$.

The infinite system was truncated to $m = 4$. The accuracy of fulfilling the boundary conditions for the specified values of geometric parameters is 10^{-4} .

Under the given boundary conditions, a stressed state arises at the interface between the layer and the inclusion. The stresses σ_ρ are shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Stresses σ_ρ in the body of the layer at the conjugation boundary; 1 – instead of inclusion – cavity; 2 – in the presence of inclusion.

If there is a void instead of the inclusion, the stresses σ_ρ are equal to zero (Fig. 1, line 1). In the presence of an inclusion (Fig. 1, line 2), the stresses σ_ρ on the conjugation boundary in the body of the layer are maximum opposite the located unit load.

Stresses σ_φ in the body of the layer at the conjugation boundary are presented in Fig. 2 in comparison with the case when there is a cavity instead of an inclusion.

Figure 2. Stress σ_φ in the body of the layer at the conjugation boundary; 1 - instead of inclusion - cavity; 2 - in the presence of inclusion.

The presence of a cavity instead of an inclusion significantly increases the stresses σ_φ on this surface, and they exceed even the specified loads (Fig. 2, line 1). Reinforcement reduces stress σ_φ (Fig. 2, line 2), reducing the risk of failure of this node.

The stresses σ_z in the body of the layer at the interface of conjugation are presented in Fig. 3 in comparison with the case when there is a cavity instead of an inclusion.

Figure 3. Stresses σ_z in the body of the layer at the conjugation boundary; 1 - instead of inclusion - cavity; 2 - in the presence of inclusion.

As can be seen from Fig. 3, in the absence of reinforcement, tensile stresses σ_z arise on the surface of the cavity (Fig. 3, line 1). The presence of reinforcement changes the sign of the stresses σ_z to negative and reduces their maximum values (Fig. 3, line 2).

Stresses $\tau_{\rho\phi}$ in the body of the layer at the conjugation boundary are presented in Fig. 4 in comparison with the case when there is a cavity instead of an inclusion.

Figure 4. Stress $\tau_{\rho\phi}$ in the body of the layer at the conjugation boundary; 1 - instead of inclusion - cavity; 2 - in the presence of inclusion.

Tangential stresses $\tau_{\rho\phi}$ in the absence of reinforcement are zero (this is given by the boundary conditions). The presence of a cylindrical inclusion increases these stresses.

Conclusions. A new spatial problem of elasticity theory for a layer located on two embedded supports and having a cylindrical inclusion is solved. The supports are represented as cylindrical cavities with prescribed displacements on them. The problem is solved using the generalized Fourier method and reduced to an infinite system of linear algebraic equations, to which the reduction method is applied.

The highly accurate results obtained allowed for a comparison of the variants of the layer with and without full-body inclusion (instead of inclusion - a cavity). Numerical analysis allows us to conclude that the presence of reinforcement reduces maximum stresses, but they are redistributed to other places, sometimes changing sign.

The method can be applied to structures whose design scheme coincides with the formulation of the given problem.

Further research is needed to replace cavities with inclusions and also to account for bulk forces.

References:

1. Tekkaya, A.E., Soyarslan, C.: Finite Element Method. Encyclopedia of Production Engineering. Berlin: Springer, 508–514 (2014).
2. Huz, A. N., Kubenko, V. D., Cherevko, M. A.: Dyfraktsiya uprugykh voln [Elastic wave diffraction]. Kyiv: Naukova Dumka, Ukraine. (1978).
3. Hrynchenko, V. T., Meleshko, V. V.: Garmonicheskiye kolebaniya i volny v uprugikh telakh [Harmonic vibrations and waves in elastic bodies]. Kyiv: Naukova Dumka, Ukraine. (1981).
4. Nykolaev, A. H., Protsenko, V. S.: Obobshchennyi metod Fur'ye v prostranstvennykh zadachakh teoryi upruhlosti [Generalized Fourier method in spatial problems of the theory of elasticity].

Kharkov: National Aerospace University "KHAU", Ukraine. (2011).

5. Nikolaev, A. G., Tanchik, E. A.: The first boundary-value problem of the elasticity theory for a cylinder with N cylindrical cavities. *Numerical Analysis and Applications*. 8, 148–158 (2015).

6. Nikolaev, A. G., Tanchik, E. A.: Stresses in an elastic cylinder with cylindrical cavities forming a hexagonal structure. *Journal of Applied Mechanics and Technical Physics*. 57, 1141–1149 (2016).

7. Nikolaev, A. G., Tanchik, E. A.: Model of the Stress State of a Unidirectional Composite with Cylindrical Fibers Forming a Tetragonal Structure. *Mechanics of Composite Materials*. 52, 177–188 (2016).

8. Ukrainets, N., Murahovska, O., Prokhorova, O.: Solving a One Mixed Problem in Elasticity Theory for Half-space With a Cylindrical Cavity by the Generalized Fourier Method. *East.-Eur. J. Enterp. Technol.* 2, 48–57 (2021).

9. Miroshnikov V. , Denysova T., Protsenko V. The study of the first main problem of the theory of elasticity for a layer with a cylindrical cavity. *Strength of Materials and Theory of Structures*. 2019. №103. P. 208–218.

10. Мірошніков В.Ю. Змішана задача теорії пружності для шару з циліндричним включенням. *Науковий вісник будівництва*. Харків, 2019. Том 2, №2(96), С. 247–252.

11. Miroshnikov V. Yu., Protsenko V.S. Determining the stress state of a layer on a rigid base weakened by several longitudinal cylindrical cavities. *Journal of Advanced Research in Technical Science*. Seattle, 2019. Iss. 17. P.11–21.

12. Miroshnikov, V., Savin, O., Younis, B., Nikichanov, V. (2022). Solution of the problem of the theory of elasticity and analysis of the stress state of a fibrous composite layer under the action of transverse compressive forces. *Eastern-European Journal of Enterprise Technologies*, 4 (7 (118)), 23–30.